

Classical Probability Theory and Quantum Wavefunctions

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In (1), we noted that a Gaussian wavefunction may be a solution to the time-independent Schrodinger equation (e.g. the ground state solution of the quantum oscillator) and simultaneously a solution of maximizing spatial Shannon's entropy $-\int \text{density}(x) \ln(\text{density}(x)) dx$ subject to the constraint $\int \text{density}(x) dx = \text{constant}$, where $\text{density}(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ with $W(x)$ being the wavefunction.

In (2), which deals strictly with classical probabilities and the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor $n(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T)$, we argued that this function is equivalent to: $\ln(n(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. This in turn is equivalent to the maximization of $\ln(n(e_i)!)$ with the constraint $\sum_i e_i n(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}}$ which is part of: $\ln(N! / \prod_i n(e_i)!)$ with the full constraint $\sum_i e_i n(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}}$. Here $n(e_i) = N p(e_i)$ where $p(e_i)$ is a probability and N a very large number. Thus a function of $\exp(\text{something})$ may indicate that "something" * density(x) is a constraint with $-\int \text{density} \ln(\text{density})$ being Shannon's entropy.

Quantum mechanics for a bound system yields a real wavefunction $W(x)$ such that $\text{density}(x) = W(x)W(x) = \text{probability}(x)$. Thus maximization of Shannon's entropy $-\int \text{density}(x) \ln(\text{density}(x)) dx$ subject to a constraint: $\int \text{density}(x) B(x) dx = \text{constant}$ should correspond to a solution for density of $\exp(-B(x))$. $B(x)$ as part of the constraint, however, should represent a physical constraint. Thus if there is a solution to the Schrodinger equation of the form $\exp(i.5B(x))$ and $B(x)\text{density}(x)$ represents the physical constraint in the system, classical maximization of probability solves the quantum problem in such a case.

The above ideas may be applied to the quantum oscillator ground state and essentially repeat what is done in (1). We, however, try to generalize them to see if they may apply to a free quantum particle. In this case the probability used is $\exp(ipx)$ which is complex. It corresponds to $P(x) = \exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$ which is a uniform distribution which has maximum lack of information.

Classical Probability, Maximization of Entropy and the Maxwell-Boltzmann Form $\exp(-e_i/T)$

In (2), we argue that the function $\exp(-e_i/T)$ is directly linked to a maximization process. In particular, $n(e_i) = Np(e_i) = C\exp(-e_i/T)$ may be written as: (with $C=1$)

$$\ln(n(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((1))$$

This has the form of a maximization problem with a constraint of $-\sum_i e_i n(e_i)/T$ with maximization of the function: $-\ln(n(e_i)!)$ using: $d/d n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)!) = \ln([n(e_i)+1]) - \ln(n(e_i))$.

$n(e_i)!$ appears in arrangement calculations. In particular, if one has probabilities $p(e_i)$ $\{n(e_i) = Np(e_i)\}$ for large N , a microstate probability is:

$$\text{Product over } i \text{ } p(e_i)^{Np(e_i)} \quad ((2))$$

All microstates have the same probability and are permutations of each other. Thus the microstate probability is:

$$1/\{\text{number of permutations}\} = 1/\{N!/\text{Product over } i \ n(e_i)\} \quad ((2))$$

because the particles are identical.

This approach should also apply to probabilities of the form $\exp(-B(x))$ where $-B(x)$ density(x) may be considered to be the physical constraint of the system.

Quantum mechanics yields a probability expression:

$$W^*(x)W(x) = \text{density}(x) \text{ and also } a^*(p)a(p) = P(p) \text{ where } W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

Thus one might try to apply the classical probability theory above to the quantum case suggesting a density(x) = $\exp(-B(x))$ or $W(x) = \exp(-.5B(x))$ for a bound state.

The Ground State Harmonic Oscillator

One example of maximization of entropy by density(x)=W(x)W(x) subject to a constraint, where W(x) is also the solution of the time-independent Schrodinger equation, is the ground state harmonic oscillator solution as already shown in (1).

In such a case, the constraint in the system is energy. For the oscillator, there is symmetry in the $p^2/2m$ and $k/2 \ x^2$ terms of energy so:

$$\text{Average KE} = \text{Average PE} \text{ and } E = 2 \text{ Average PE} \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{An energy constraint is: } \int E \text{ density}(x)dx = 2 \int .5kx^2 \text{ density}(x) dx \quad ((5))$$

Thus one may maximize Shannon's entropy $-\text{density}(x) \ln(\text{density})$ subject to the constraint ((5)). This yields a Gaussian solution which has been shown in (1).

Thus this solution satisfies both the Schrodinger time-independent equation and classical entropy maximization.

Free Quantum Particle

We wish to consider trying to generalize the ideas discussed above. We have noted before the similarity of the free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ with $\exp(-ei/T)$ and argued that both represent statistical quantities which have the same property:

$$P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_1+e_2) \text{ and } P_1(p_1)P_1(p_2)=P_1(p_3) \quad ((6))$$

We write $P_1(p)$ because it represents the "kind of probability" $\exp(ipx)$.

We argued in ((2)) that this is essentially the property required to write:

$$\ln(P(e_i)) = \text{constant } e_i \quad ((7a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \ln(P_1(p)) = ipx \quad ((7b))$$

In ((7a)), the constant is positive and so the RHS side is of the form: $d/dP(e_i) e_i P(e_i)$ and the LHS $d/d P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i)!)$. Thus one maximizes an “arrangement” type of expression subject to a constraint in order to obtain $P(e_i)$.

The factor in ((7b)) is purely imaginary. If one may generalize the procedure used for the real probability in the oscillator ground state, one might argue that one has a kind of maximization of Shannon’s entropy using the complex $\exp(ipx)$ as the probability density. Then, maximization of:

$$-P_1(x) \ln(P_1(x)) + ipx P_1(x) \quad \text{with respect to } P_1(x) \text{ yields} \rightarrow P_1(x) = \exp(ipx) \quad ((8))$$

In this case the constraint is linked with average momentum p , but energy is $pave^2/2m$ so this is fine. Nevertheless a kind of “maximum” entropy solution is found, but pertaining to a complex probability i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. Thus we suggest that maximization of entropy may exist even at a complex wavefunction level. $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$ which is a uniform distribution which represents maximum uncertainty i.e. no special information about any x versus another.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the form $\exp(-e_i/T)$ is equivalent to: $\ln(n(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. This, in turn, is linked to the maximization of: $\ln(n(e_i)!) = -e_i n(e_i)/T$ through $d/d n(e_i)$. Thus one essentially has a maximization of Shannon’s entropy subject to a constraint solution. We argue that wavefunctions in quantum mechanics which are of the form: $\exp(\text{something})$, where something is linked to the physical constraint in the system, may represent maximum classical entropy solutions. In (1) we already showed this is the case for the ground state of the quantum oscillator. In that case: something = constant $.5kxx$ where the constraint of energy may be written as: $2 \int dx \text{density}(x) .5kxx$ with $\text{density}=W(x)W(x)$.

In this note, we try to extend these ideas to a free quantum particle with a kind of probability $P_1(x)=\exp(ipx)$. ipx seems to be a suitable constraint when multiplied by $P_1(x)$ as it is linked to p . We apply the maximization of Shannon’s entropy subject using P_1 with the constraint $ipx P_1$. This leads to $P_1(x)=\exp(ipx)$. We suggest that even though one uses complex probabilities and a somewhat different type of constraint, one has maximum entropy type solutions at the wavefunction level. The spatial density: $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$ which represents a uniform density which is one with a maximum lack of information i.e. no information distinguishing one x point from another.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Gaussians as Both Solutions of the Schrodinger Equation and Maximum Entropy Calculation (preprint, zenodo, 2018)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Degeneracy, Average Occupancy and Microstates in Statistical Mechanics Part II (preprint, zenodo, 2023)